

Bulgaria

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Bulgaria, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system and complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in national systems, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<https://www.eter-project.eu/>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, the Bulgarian higher education system comprises higher education establishments with accreditation from the National Evaluation and Accreditation Agency and established under terms and procedure determined by The Higher Education Act (HEA)²:

- Universities
- Specialized Higher Education Schools
- Independent Colleges

Universities are higher education establishments which educate on a wide circle of specialities, of professional sectors in at least three of the four basic spheres of the science - humanitarian, natural, social and technical for the degrees Bachelor, Master and Doctor in the respective basic spheres of science. Universities have academic personnel, a material base which provides the practical education in compliance with the state requirements and possess a library and a university information centre for administrative servicing of students and PhD students. They have scientific, artistic and creative potential and possess a system for protection of intellectual property. Higher education establishments which carry out education in one or two basic spheres of the science or culture and meet the requirements of HEA, can be universities with a name expressing its specifics. Research universities are higher education institutions which, apart from the other characteristics of a university, make a significant contribution to the development of important public domains through state-of-the-art research. Their results are assessed according to objective indicators defined in an act adopted by the Council of Ministers.

The **Specialized Higher Education Schools** carry out scientific research or artistic and creative work and provide education in one of the basic spheres of science, art, physical culture and meet the requirements of HEA. The name of the establishment expresses the specific sphere where it prepares specialists. This higher education establishment alongside with the Bachelor degree may also educate in educational qualification

¹ <https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/bulgaria/types-higher-education-institutions>

² In its tertiary education statistics the National Statistical Institute includes the private spiritual higher schools until the 2021/2022 academic year. Due to a change in the Religious Denominations Act, the three spiritual higher schools are out of the scope since 2022/2023 academic year.

degree Master and educational and scientific degree Doctor. A higher education school that makes a significant contribution to the development of important public areas through top scientific research and has high research results, evaluated according to objective indicators, (including the number of published and referenced scientific articles in international databases, number of applications for international patents filed, number of citations in refereed and indexed journals by other authors in international databases), determined by an act of the Council of Ministers, may be designated as a Research Higher Education School.

Independent Colleges offer professional training and qualification, following high school graduation, in highly specialized areas of higher education and in this way offer their graduates direct access to the labour market. They award a Professional Bachelor requiring a minimum of 180 credits and at least three years length of the study.

Colleges may also be established **within a University or a Specialized Higher Education School**, having obtained accreditation in professional branches or specialties from regulated professions. Such Colleges must offer a Bachelor degree with at least 240 credits with a minimum length of studies of four years.

Moreover, the training for the educational and scientific degree Doctor can be carried out in accredited doctoral programs in the **Bulgarian Academy of Science**, the **Agricultural Academy**, the **national centres** for the problems of the public health and other scientific organizations.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Universities are mostly public institutions and, with very few exceptions, have the right to award PhDs. In total, about 80% of all Bulgarian HEIs are Universities and equivalent institutions. The 3 Independent Colleges play a more limited role and are not awarding PhDs.

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category		N	Public	Private	PhD awarding
Independent college	Самостоятелен колеж	3	0	3	0
Scientific organization	Научна организация	1	1	0	1
University	Университет	48	38	10	43
Total		52	39	13	44

Note: Numbers reflect inclusion in ETER

Complementary, the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS), as a public scientific institution, is the leading scientific center in Bulgaria. It carries out scientific and applied research in nine divisions covering all areas of human knowledge produces about half of the scientific output in the country. The BAS is accredited to teach PhD students in dozens of programs. Together with Higher Education Institutions from and outside Bulgaria, training programs are organized for students in the Bachelor and Master degrees.

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of Bulgaria's higher education and its evolution over time. Figure 1 shows that the expansion of the system in terms of the number of HEIs is relatively recent. With the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (founded in 1869), the Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, the oldest Bulgarian university (1888), and the National Academy of Art (1896), only three HEI were founded before the 20th century. Only 9 of the Bulgarian HEIs were founded before World War II. The Independent Colleges have a tradition going back to the late Nineteenth Century. However, it was only in the 1990s that they underwent several reforms, and as a result, they are part of the HEI sector today.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Note: Figure 1 comprises only institutions that existed in 2020 and were active in the given foundation year.

Institutions that have ceased to exist before 2020 are not included in this figure, so the given number may not be identical to the actual number of institutions that were active in the foundation year.

Students

In terms of the number of students enrolled, Universities are the dominant HEI sector in Bulgaria; according to ETER data they account for 99% of all students (ISCED5-7) in 2020, whereas, with a share of 1%, Colleges play only a minor role (see Figure 2). Hereby, the public HEIs are dominant: while 75% of the HEI institutions in Bulgaria are public, they account for 88% of the students, according to ETER data. The Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (BAS) does not teach undergraduate students. Also, we observe systematic differences between HEI types with respect to the educational levels, which can be associated with differing institutional mandates. While, according to ETER data, Independent Colleges account for 1% of the Bachelor students, no higher level degrees are offered. In comparison, 6% of the Doctoral students are enrolled at the BAS which, with its exceptional mission in scientific research, is the only non-university HEI to offer ISCED8 teaching³. In absolute numbers, 5,963 PhD students are enrolled at universities, and 405 PhD students at the BAS.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Total students include ISCED 5-7

³ There are thirteen other scientific organizations in Bulgaria training PhD students but are not covered by ETER and therefore do not enter this report.

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, by levels of seniority.

As shown by Figure 3, there is a huge difference between Bulgarian HEI sectors in size, with more than 30,700 persons employed at Universities and 104 employed at Independent Colleges, as measured by head counts (HC) in 2020. In Bulgaria, universities are also by far larger institutions in terms of total personnel, with an average size of 591 HC, as compared with 35 HC at Colleges. In both HEI types, about two thirds of the personnel (in HC) are academic personnel.

Figure 3. Personnel (HC) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Note: Data on Research and teaching assistants is missing.

For 2020 onwards, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT⁴. Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e., career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e., the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

⁴ OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

As for Bulgaria, comparable data on staff seniority and gender is available only for Universities and Independent Colleges (Figure 4). Data combining these two sectors shows that the major share of academic personnel (57%) is “junior academic personnel”, with a decent majority of employees being women (56%), as measured by head counts. Intermediate academic personnel amounts to 28% of the academic staff (HC), already with a majority of men (52%) over women (48%), indicating that the leaky pipeline already takes a significant effect at the intermediate level of seniority. The share of females further drops to 41% (HC) of senior academic personnel, a level of representation though, which in international comparison is still relatively high.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

Note: Only Universities and Independent colleges included.

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of enrolled students in Bulgarian HEIs, data show a pattern of steady decrease from 2011 to 2020, with an especially strong reduction from 2014 to 2017 (Figure 5). This dramatic development is shown in both HEI sectors, Universities and Colleges. In 2020, enrolment in the Universities amounted to 78% of the student numbers Bulgaria had in 2011, and in the Independent Colleges the drop was even stronger, arriving at 55% of the 2011 numbers. From 2015 onwards, Colleges were integrated in the university sector, causing the Colleges sector to disappear in 2020. Hereby, the overall number of institutions remained stable in this decade (see Figure 1). This development of decreasing student numbers is widely attributed to a number of factors, the most prevalent being demographic factors (low birth rates and emigration) and education system issues (outdated curricula, inadequate facilities) in Bulgaria. However, these developments are not evenly distributed across educational disciplines: According to the EC’s Education and

Training Monitor 2023⁵, student numbers have increased significantly in ICT, education, mathematics and statistics, arts and health but decreased sharply in several programmes like environment, forestry, engineering and biology.

Figure 5. Number of students enrolled by institutional type, 2011-2020

As shown by Figure 6, also employment in the Bulgarian HEI sector has significantly decreased from 2011 to 2020. Despite some fluctuations in the early 2010s, total academic personnel at the Universities has decreased by 8 percentage points in this decade. We observe an even stronger reduction in the Colleges, where in 2020 the total academic personnel is only 63% of the 2011 level. The reasons for this structural change – an adaptation to student enrolment – might be seen in the above-mentioned more general developments in Bulgaria. At least, as regards the universities, the reduction in total academic staff seems to be cushioned.

⁵ <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/eac/education-and-training-monitor-2023/en/country-reports/bulgaria.html#5-higher-education>

Figure 6. Academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

The “Implementation of the Strategy for the Development of Higher Education in the Republic of Bulgaria 2021-2030” foresees support for the development of the academic staff in higher schools and scientific organizations, including increasing interest and improving conditions for doctoral programs related to the needs of the labour market. This happens through the support of modular programs and through the implementation of the National Program “Improving the competences of teachers from public higher education institutions which prepare teachers”. In the period 2021 - 2023, the procedure “Modernization of higher education institutions” comprises a number of support measures with the participation of 32. Among those are distance learning programs, digitalisation of education, collaboration of the BAS, Agricultural Academy and higher schools for joint masters and doctorates, as well as international cooperations aiming at double degrees.

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